

INTRODUCING THE CONCEPT OF BACK-INKING AS AN EFFICIENT MODEL FOR DOCUMENT RETRIEVAL (IMAGE RECONSTRUCTION)

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ABSTRACT

Today, many institutions and organizations are facing serious problem due to the tremendously increasing size of documents, and this problem is further triggering the storage and retrieval problems due to the continuously growing space and efficiency requirements. This increase in the size and number of documents is becoming a complex problem in most offices. Therefore, there is a demand to address this challenging problem. This can be met by developing a technique to enable specialized document imaging people to use when there is a need for storing documents images. Thus, there is a need for an efficient retrieval technique for this type of information retrieval (IR) systems.

In this paper, we present an efficient retrieval technique for electronic documents. The Back-Inking concept is proposed as an efficient technique for certain image formats. The use of this approach is a continuation of the SIPA [32] approach which was presented in an earlier paper as an efficient method for document storage, and as a result makes the image retrieval relatively efficient.

KEYWORDS

Information Pixels, Document Retrieval, Document Segmentation, Image Formats, Back-Inking

1. INTRODUCTION

By using SIPA technique, we learned how we can store the addresses of information pixels and how it helps in minimizing the storage size of the image components. We also analyzed the time consumed to convert an image from its respective format into an array of addresses.

There is a practical significance of this analysis. By converting an image into our format, we are saving the image not as an array with pixel intensity values but as an array with the addresses of information pixels. The time taken to convert the image into such an array is in reality the time taken to save the image in our format. Analogously, if retrieving the image saved in our format is the purpose, in reality we will be converting the array of addresses of information pixels into an image. The time taken to open the image saved in our format must be equivalent to converting the

array into an image. In this research paper, we retrieve the image from the array of addresses by applying a technique that we shall call "Back-Inking".

2. BACK-INKING ALGORITHM

As the name implies, in this technique, we work backwards and replace an information pixel to where the address in the array points to. The addresses of information pixels are stored in the array. Every row in the array is made up of 2 elements. The first element is a pointer that points to the row and the second element is a pointer that points to a column. Together, they work as a 2-dimensional pointer pointing to the original location of the information pixel in an image.

The algorithm places a black pixel at the address pointed by the array and the remaining pixels are white.

The Back-Inking Algorithm does the following:

- An array of size ($m \times n$) is formed with all values in it being 256. This represents an image with all pixels white. Let us call it image R. Here m and n are the corresponding numbers of rows and columns (the coordinates) in the original image.
- The algorithm reads the first row in the array of addresses. It contains 2 elements.
- It points to the row in image R corresponding to the first element among the 2 values read.
- It then points to the column in image R corresponding to the second element among the 2 values read.
- This pixel formed by the row-column intersection of addresses is replaced with the value 0.
- The algorithm next reads the second row in the array of addresses and points to the pixel corresponding to that address in image R. This pixel value is replaced by 0.
- The process repeats till the algorithm reads all rows in the array of addresses and replaces the pixels in image R corresponding to those addresses by 0.

Example: Let us simulate this algorithm for a BMP image with 150 pixels per inch.

Step 1: Create an array of size (1327 X 1004) with each value in it being 256. This image is called R.

This represents an image with intensity 256 all through. Hence the image is white. This is an initialization process. We replace white pixels with black ones according to the address stored in the array.

Step 2: The first element in the array of addresses corresponding to this image is read.

We have seen in previous research paper [32] that the array of addresses that corresponds to a BMP image of 150 pixels per inch has a size of (43266 X 2). Let us call this array Array1. The first row of the array gets read, that is, Array1(1,1) and Array1(1,2).

Array1 (1,1)=1; Array (1,2)=241;

Step 3: The algorithm points to the first row in image R.

This is because it points to the row in image R corresponding to the first element read, that is, Array1 (1,1)=1.

Step 4: It then points to the 241st column in image R.

This is because it points to the column in image R corresponding to the second element read, that is,

Array1 (1,2)=241.

Step 5: The pixel formed by the row-column intersection in step 3 and in step 4 is replaced by a 0.

Intensity 0 corresponds to black. We have now replaced a black pixel at location (1,241).

Step 6: The same process repeats for each row of Array1 and hence all addresses present in Array1 are replaced by a 0 in image R, that is, a black pixel in image R. We shall call this the "Back-Inking Process".

3. MATLAB SIMULATION OF BACK-INKING ALGORITHM

Previously, we have used MATLAB to store the image in the form of an array of addresses. We will now simulate the conversion of array of addresses into an image in MATLAB. A snippet of the code that is used for reconstruction of the image is shown below.

```
% Start counter to keep a tab of the time  
tic;  
% Reconstructed array  
Rearray=uint8(255*ones(m,n));  
for l=1:lgth  
rearray(Array(l,1),Array(l,2))=0;  
end  
figure(2)  
imshow(rearray)  
% End of time counter  
toc;
```

1. Here *tic* and *toc* commands are used to keep a tab of the time. They return the time taken to convert the array of addresses into an image.
2. *Rearray=uint8(255*ones(m,n));*

We initialize the reconstructed image (called *rearray*) with all intensity values 255.

Here

m- Number of rows in the image;

n- Number of columns in the image;

ones (m,n) will create an array of size (*m X n*) with all values in it being 1.

*255*ones(m,n)* will multiply each value in the array *ones (m,n)* by 255. Hence each value in the array is now initialized to 255.

uint 8 is a function used to convert numbers from any data type to the type- *uint8*. This is because images are supposed to be in the form *uint8* in MATLAB. *uint8* has a range (0 – 255) which matches the intensity range in 8-bit grayscale images.

```
1. for l=1:lgth  
rearray(Array(l,1),Array(l,2))=0;  
end
```

This part of the program is used to replace each pixel in the image *rearray* with an intensity value 0. The address of the pixel is pointed by the array of addresses (called *Array*).

Here *lgth*= number of rows in the array.

The *for* loop:

```
for l=1:lgth  
.....  
End
```

executes the statement within the loop *#lgth* number of times and in each iteration, the value of *l* is incremented by 1. The start value of *l* is 1 and its stop value is *#lgth*.

The statement within the *for* loop is:

```
Rearray(Array(l,1),Array(l,2))=0
```

As explained in the example above, the initial value in the *for* loop is *Array(1,1)=1* and *Array(1,2)=241*.

Here, *rearray(Array(l,1),Array(l,2))*, i.e., *rearray(1,241)=0*;

For each iteration in the *for* loop, successive values of addresses stored in *Array* are read and the corresponding values in *rearray* are replaced by 0. Since the *for* loop ends at *l=lgth*, the last iteration is executed till the last element in *Array* is read and a 0 is replaced in its corresponding location in the image.

2. *Imshow(rearray)* is used to display the reconstructed image.

The same snippet of code can be used for all image formats with different dpi and for both full body segments of the scanned document image and the whole A4 scanned document image types.

For the same dpi, since the size of the full body image is smaller than that of an A4 size image; the number of information pixels in a full body image is lesser, the size of its corresponding array of addresses is smaller and hence it will take lesser time to be reconstructed into an image when compared to its A4 counterpart.

Table (1) below shows the reconstruction time and the average viewable mark of the reconstructed images for different resolutions of the Whole KSU Document images.

No	IMAGE FORMAT (TYPE)	IMAGE RESOLUTION (DPI)	IMAGE RECONSTRUCTION TIME (Seconds)	IMAGE EVALUATION POINTS (10)
1	GIF	75	1.8223	6.2
2		100	1.6245	6.9
3		150	7.8764	8.9
4		200	23.4180	9.7
5	BMP	75	0.8154	7.8
6		100	1.7831	8.6
7		150	8.4214	9.2
8		200	24.2599	9.6
9	JPG	75	1.4210	5.9
10		100	3.6006	7.1
11		150	14.6970	8.6
12		200	59.8907	9.1
13	TIF	75	0.7510	6.3
14		100	1.5989	7.9
15		150	7.7328	8.9
16		200	19.2055	9.6

Table (1)

4 . MATLAB CODES AND RECONSTRUCTED IMAGES

Now we are ready to see the MATLAB codes and reconstructed images for the examined image types for different image resolutions for both the whole KSU A4 document and for the Full Body Segment images.

The code below is the code for reconstructing (Back-Inking) the whole A4 Document (.gif) format image scanned with (150) dpi.

```
clear all; close all; clc;
tic;
RGBimage = imread( 'C:\Users\ALGhalayini_rn\ a4size\gif\full page 256 colors 8bit 150.gif',
'gif' );
GRAYimage = RGBimage;
figure ( 1 );
imshow ( GRAYimage );
```

```

m = length ( GRAYimage );
n = length ( GRAYimage ( 1 , : ) );
total_pixels = m * n;
k = 1;
for i = 1 : m
for j = 1 : n
if GRAYimage ( i , j ) < 128
    Array1 ( 1 , k ) = i; Array2 ( 1 , k ) = j;
    k = k + 1;
end
end
end

Array = [Array1' Array2'];
Toc
    
```

Table (2) below shows the reconstruction time and the average viewable mark of the reconstructed images for different resolutions of the Full Body Segment Images.

No	IMAGE FORMAT (TYPE)	IMAGE RESOLUTION (DPI)	IMAGE RECONSTRUCTION TIME (Seconds)	IMAGE EVALUATION POINTS (10)
1	GIF	75	0.6415	5.1
2		100	1.4724	6.8
3		150	6.1677	9.0
4		200	12.8715	9.7
5	BMP	75	0.7326	4.1
6		100	1.4580	5.9
7		150	6.1659	8.1
8		200	12.6825	9.1
9	JPG	75	0.7860	6.4
10		100	1.7775	7.1
11		150	6.8940	8.9
12		200	12.8280	9.8
13	TIF	75	0.6282	6.3
14		100	1.4001	7.1
15		150	6.1385	8.5
16		200	12.9299	9.2

Table (2)

Figure (1) below shows the reconstructed Image after applying the Back-Inking Method the whole A4 Document (.gif) format image scanned with (150) dpi

Figure (1)

The code below is the code for reconstructing (Back-Inking) the Full Body (.tif) format image scanned with (150) dpi.

```
clear all; close all; clc;
tic;
RGBImage = imread( 'C:\Users\ALGhalayini_rn\FulNtif\full page 256 colors 8bit 150.tif', 'tif' );
GRAYImage = rgb2gray ( RGBImage );
figure ( 1 );
imshow ( GRAYImage ( 454 : 1459 , 118 : 1122 ) );
m = length ( GRAYImage );
n = length ( GRAYImage ( 1 , : ) );
total_pixels = m * n;
k = 1;
for i = 454 : 1459
for j = 118 : 1122
if GRAYImage ( i , j ) < 128
    Array1 ( 1 , k ) = i; Array2 ( 1 , k ) = j;
    k = k + 1;
end
end
end
Array = [Array1' Array2'];
Toc
```

Figure (2) below shows the reconstructed Image after applying the Back-Inking Method the Full Body Segment (.tif) format image scanned with (150) dpi

Figure (2)

5. CONCLUSION

Our goal in this research paper was to introduce the concept of **Back-Inking** which is the procedure to retrieve the stored addresses of the Information pixels from the array and plot black

pixels back into the white page to reconstruct the whole image back, then display it to the user in a relatively short time.

We observe that the reconstructed images for all formats are better in quality, in that, as the dpi increases, the sharpness of the image increases. But as the dpi increases the time to reconstruct the image also increases. Through applying this method, we came up with the following conclusions:

- The time taken to retrieve an image in a specific format with lesser dpi is less than the time taken to retrieve an image in the same format with larger dpi. Hence, this is a time/complexity-quality tradeoff.
- Full body images of a specific format and dpi take lesser time to be executed than its A4 size image counterpart.
- Considering the above 2 factors, the complexity and time of image retrieval increases as we move from 75 to 200 dpi. It takes lesser time to retrieve a full body segment scanned image than an A4 scanned image. We can therefore conclude that using 150 dpi full body segment scanned images produces an optimum result because :
- Retrieval of images with 150 dpi do not take as much time as images with 200 dpi;
- Retrieval of an image with 150 dpi is not as complex as an image with 200 dpi because the number of information pixels are lesser in images with 150 dpi and hence lesser the size of the array of addresses.
- The quality of images is certainly better than images with 75,100

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